

NUMERICAL MODELING OF ADHESIVELY BONDED CFRP JOINTS CONSIDERING NON-LINEAR DEFORMATION OF ADHESIVE LAYERS

S. Mimura^{1*}, T. Abe², T. Kusaka², N. Mori², K. Takagi³, M. Hojo¹, M. Nishikawa¹, and N. Matsuda¹

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University, Kyoto, Japan

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Ritsumeikan University, Kusatsu, Japan

³ Integrated Defense & Space Systems, Mitsubishi Heavy Industries, Nishi-kasugai, Japan

Introduction

- The structural integrity of adhesive joints can be evaluated using fracture mechanics [1] [2].
- The evaluation of fracture toughness requires a complete understanding about the non-linear behavior of adhesive layers.

Aim

- The evaluation method for the fracture toughness of adhesive joints from the view point of the non-linear behavior
- Numerical method which can detect fracture in both adhesives and adherends

Experiments

Mode II fracture toughness tests

- ENF tests with large and small bending spans
- The fracture toughness G_{IIc} was calculated taking into account of non-linear deformation of adhesive layers [3].

→ The results of large and small ENF tests were comparable.

[1] B.R.K. Blackman, A.J. Kinloch, M. Paraschi, Engineering Fracture Mechanics, Vol. 72, pp.877–897, (2005).

[2] M.F.S.F. de Moura, R.D.S.G. Campilho, J.P.M. Gonçalves, International Journal of Solids and Structures, Vol. 46, pp.1589–1595, (2009).

[3] S. Inakazu, et al. JSME M&M 2018, OS0224, Fukui, Japan, 2018.

Numerical Analyses

Modeling methods

Simulations for the large 4ENF specimen was studied.

The adhesive layer was modeled with:

- Model S: elastic-plastic solid elements
- Model C: cohesive elements
- Model S + C: cohesive elements embedded in elastic-plastic solid elements

Material properties

- Adherends: elastic orthotropic
- Adhesives (solid elements): elastic-plastic isotropic
- Adhesives (cohesive elements): bilinear traction-separation law

E_1 [GPa]	E_2 [GPa]	G_{12} [GPa]	ν_{12}	E_{ad} [GPa]
135	7.2	3.6	0.34	1.96

Results

- The macroscopic load-displacement behavior was successfully reproduced in each model.

Crack extension

- The crack onset of Model C was comparable to the experimental results, whereas in Model S + C it occurred at a lower load.
- The whole results of Model S + C were not comparable with the experimental result, whereas the results of Model C were comparable with the experimental results.

Stress distribution

- The shear stress distribution along the adherend-adhesive interface was predicted correctly in the Model S and the Model S + C.

Crack extension behavior

Shear stress distribution along the adhesive interface